

The Political Discourse in “*Animal Farm*” by George Orwell: A Critical Discourse Study

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Abstract

Animal Farm is considered one of the creations of political and social criticism, as Orwell established a satirical method in achieving a kind of humor to disdain the communist regime and criticize the dictatorial policy, using animals as a type of disparagement of the ruling class, because they were characterized by the dictatorial tone covered by socialism and democracy, and this is what made the author accurate even in choosing characters, method of dialogue, and moving between events. This paper is a critical discourse analysis (CDA) of political ideology in “*Animal Farm*”. A limited number of studies have applied essential theories of discourse to literary work in general and modern fiction in particular. Rogti (2019) studies the techniques in teaching English literature according to CDA. Yasa (2020) examines students' abilities to analyze literary works in higher studies, according to CDA.

Moreover, Hossain (2022) studied Critical Discourse Analysis of Literary Texts from classes two to eight. To fill this gap in the study, the researchers use van Dijk's (1998) *ideological square* and Wodak's (2001; 2009) *discourse-historical*. This study aimed to analyze the false democratic character and the artificial democratic representation represented by the government that came through the revolution to make it a type of rule and control over the people and also to analyze the characters according to the political representation and literary motive.

Keywords: *Animal Farm*, CDA, Democracy, Dictatorial, Socialism, and Orwell.

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1- Literature Review

One of the controversial novels in contemporary literature because of its political, social and literary dimensions, this novel includes the symbolic thought of literary works very directly, as Orwell created a method for political reflection in which he revived the novelist's role to embody humans in an important dialectical way that resulted in the human failure of the claimant. Equality and justice in leading the masses appropriately, as the controversy is based on representing a man with animals, giving the animal the role and full eligibility to describe man, and creating symbolism that provides the novel with a bright color for political and social study and analysis, as though studying the characters, time, and place, a clear idea is united, such as the writer's motivation in choosing the farm. A place that represents the homeland and the land that bears all these events, along with a number of components that are full of obstacles and loopholes, as is the case with all homelands.

Animal Farm expresses political controversy and human failure in forming an aspiring political and social ideology and in support of the failure of a dictatorship. Orwell divided contemporary political thought on a closed ground that has always sparked controversy in the political community, which is "Russia" and the transitional and highly controversial state this region holds. During one period, that is, during the time of Soviet rule, the political ramifications and social fluctuations that followed that rule, along with the sterile nature of the rule, led to Russian society being plunged into brutal wars in which a huge number of people were killed. Therefore, after that, it became a type of political transition and social and cultural openness for a temporary period, and the trend toward relative stability on the level of Soviet territory after the departure of Khrushchev, Stalin, Andrei Gorbachev and others, the political and social scene and the departure of dictatorial and war ideas and party fanaticism. This period left a state of loss of vast lands and enormous areas that were controlled by the Soviets and ruled over with iron and fire, followed by a new rule characterized by dual democracy. The aspects of most transitional political processes are the hope of plunging society and the ruling class into a contemporary ideology, which is "democracy," despite the fact that this "modern" rule came as a complement to the late Soviet thought, but with a new look and an innovative modern system "according to the claim," and since this system is not traditional for that reason. It became democratic but adhered

to Soviet socialism as a successful system of government, according to the "leaders' point of view." As soon as the region stabilized and calmed down, the spirit of competition in the interior returned and spread abroad, followed by a number of political fluctuations that always accompany social, cultural, and economic volatility.

What Orwell conveyed in his literary way created a set of symbols that reflect the lived reality in that region and period. When the animals decided to declare a revolution against the humans in charge of the farm, the motive was the inability to lead the farm and the animals appropriately and that the animals have the right to choose a democratic life without entering into the conflicts that humans engage in between each other and with the animals, and this is what caused the creation of a crisis on that farm. "And here we must stop for a moment and look at the political movements that oppose Soviet rule, the state of society, and the orientation and class that these animals represent." Then, like the rest of the revolutions, the animals, such as the fat pig and other pigs, the horse, the rich man's mare, and others, begin to move towards destabilizing matters and broadcasting news that motivates the public to move, and then the writer moves in the direction of. He gave political eligibility to these animals. In return, he chose the shapes of animals in a satirical manner that represented the ruling class at the time and the revolutionary groups. He gave satire enough room to play an active role with innovative symbolism to create this different embodiment of the ruling class and opposition to it.

For example, he chose both:

- The Fat Pig (Napoleon) was a reflection of the leader Joseph Stalin and represented power, political corruption, modern dictatorship, and social decadence.
- Another pig (Snowball): this is a (political) reflection of Trotsky, the revolutionary aspirant, who was driven by the principles of the Bolshevik Revolution, which meant aspiring to modern socialism.
- The Old Pig (our brother): a reflection of the Marxist socialist thinker (Karl Marx), the owner of the Marxist principle and the greatest supporter of the socialist movement as a principle of governance and a type of popular base for social unification and democratic (social-political) sharing, as it represents political and inspiring support for the masses revolting against people in farm.

- The little pig (Scott): which is the media supports Napoleon (the fat pig), as Scott works to polish Napoleon's image in front of the public so that he appears in a good appearance and the dictatorial deportations do not appear on him, as Napoleon remained in power and the features of a dictator appeared on him, as Orwell deliberately made Scott a little pig as a kind of mockery towards the fake, sycophantic media.
- The horse (Molly) represents the ruling class in the newly emerging authority, immersed in prosperity and well-being, expresses greed, political and social corruption, and the unreal image of the new, hardworking farm society.
- The horse (Boxer): This horse represents the hardworking class that works with sincerity and dedication, which is characterized by morals and sincerity, and which always does not receive anything deserved, despite dedication, sincerity, and hard work.

2. Critical Discourse Analysis

Critical Discourse analysis (CDA) is a wide-ranging term with various definitions that "integrates a whole palette of meanings" ranging from linguistics, philosophy, sociology, and other disciplines. (Titscher et al., 1998, p. 42). Furthermore, CDA has an assumption that language is constantly understood according to the political, social, and economic cultural context ((Fairclough, 1995; Yasa, 2020, p.33). Consequently, critical discourse analysis can also be used in learning, such as in developing critical thinking skills when reading literary works, as they contain ideologies, abuse of power, and hidden agendas. (Yasa, 2020, p.33). CDA is a method and a theory that can be used to find and explain hidden agendas in literature. These hidden agendas can affect the reader's ideology, whether it is consciously or not (Zabihi, 2011: 8).

The term "discourse" was found back in the 14th century. It is derived from the Latin word "discursus", which means a "conversation." (Mahmood & Majeed, 2019, p.68). According to the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (2001: 388), discourse is defined as "a serious speech or piece of writing on a particular subject". Stubbs (1983, p. 1) states that discourse is "language above the sentence or above the clause" and "the study of discourse is the study of any aspect of language use." Meanwhile, Fairclough argues that "discourse constitutes three dimensions of society: knowledge, social relations and social identity – and these correspond

respectively to three major functions of language ... Discourse is shaped by relations of power and invested ideologies” (Fairclough, 1992, p. 8).

Van Dijk (1998B:353) stresses that Critical Discourse analysis is not "a unitary theoretical framework or a specific direction". CDA has four distinctive approaches. The first approach is Critical Linguistics which was developed by Fowler, Kress, Hodge & Trew (1979), Kress (1985), Fowler (1991, 1996), and Kress & Hodge (1979). The second approach was established by Fairclough (1989, 1992, and 1995), known as the Socio-cultural approach. Wodak (1996, 2001) developed the third approach, known as "the Discourse-Historical approach". Lastly, Van Dijk (1998, 2001) anticipated the sociocognitive approach (Aldihaymawee, Sharifi, & Alizadeh, 2021, P.777).

3- Discussion

The Literary Dimension in the Novel "*Animal Farm*"

1. Sarcasm: Orwell used sarcasm in most aspects of the novel and highlighted the spirit of power, political tyranny, and the beginning and end of revolutions. Orwell used the style of sarcasm to address serious issues funnily, such as choosing animals, their names, shapes, their way of talking, and the type of language used by each character.
2. The Symbolic Dimension: *Animal Farm* is characterized by different forms of symbols that express modern political and social concepts, and this is what gives the novel a literary depth with a depth of performance in the text that allows for different types of analysis, criticism and interpretation.
3. Rebuking Political Regimes: Orwell expressed his attack on corrupt and dictatorial political regimes, which made political satire and the representation of political reality with a literary dimension important in the novel, as he presented a critical vision of power and its nature, the way revolutionaries penetrated the political lobby, transformed their methodology and revolutionary nature, and transformed the principles of the revolution into personal gains and transformed them. The method of achieving successful political action and depicting the extent of corruption in human societies and transferring it to animal society is what made this novel interesting for criticism and analysis, as the

attempt to change to create a state of integration failed after the animals also were unable to lead and implement the democratic role with a socialist tendency.

Therefore, when Orwell took power from humans and gave it to animals, the intention was not that the animal was incapable of leadership after failing to implement justice and equality on the farm, but rather that humans have a great nature of corruption and dictatorship, and after granting the ability to rule to animals and their failure to lead, it came to convey the state of the human being as a dictator. A failure in governance is just like an animal, and political systems that follow the principle of dictatorship and political dissolution and sink into corruption are failures, whether their leader is a human or an animal.

4. Conclusion

It is not possible for a human being to be qualified as a dictator to rule in the modern era, as this character has passed with the vanished decades that failed miserably, such as the failure that occurred the farm that was under the control of dictatorial ruling humans and the inability of animals after their socialist democratic idea turned into a class dictatorship. In the end, Orwell concluded his novel with the failure of Napoleon's pig system, with great disappointment on the part of the animals, especially those represented by the horse Boxer and his companions, after the failure of Napoleon and his companions to lead them towards a safe shore or social democracy after the divisions on the farm became great and its society turned to classism as disgusting as the affluent (class). High in society, such as Boxer), farmers and workers (the impoverished class of society, such as Molly), the disappearance of the values that the revolution brought and which the old pig (Akhna) always chanted the disappearance of the role of the group and the emergence of the role of authority and fanaticism in governance.

Through the symbolism available in the novel, the most important questions in the novel remain:

- Why did Orwell take power away from humans and give it to animals?
- Are animals symbolically more “qualified” to rule than humans?

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